

Overcoming Bell's Palsy Via Combination Therapy- A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Bell palsy is the most common paralysis of the seventh cranial nerve, with an onset that is typically rapid and hemifacial. The condition affects 15 to 40 of every 100,000 people annually and recurs in approximately 10% of cases. In addition to unilateral facial paralysis, Bell palsy often also involves a prodrome of otalgia, and many patients additionally report ipsilateral xerophthalmia, epiphora, hyperacusis, nasal obstruction, and dysgeusia. This is a case report of 70 years old male showing symptoms of Bell's Palsy that is diagnosed to be secondary to Herpes Zoster Infection. The patient was prescribed with combination of antiviral and corticosteroid medication for relief of symptoms and cause. The literature shows that the outcome of patients treated with corticosteroid plus acyclovir was superior to the outcome of those treated with prednisone plus placebo and thus this combination therapy was taken into consideration.

KEYWORDS

Seventh cranial nerve, Facial paralysis, Corticosteroid, Antiviral, Bell's Palsy

INTRODUCTION

The most prevalent acute mono-neuropathy, or condition affecting a single nerve, is Bell's palsy, named after Scottish anatomist Sir Charles Bell. It is the most common diagnosis associated with facial nerve weakening or paralysis[1]. It is defined as an acute, unilateral paresis or paralysis of the face in a pattern consistent with peripheral nerve dysfunction, without detectable causes[2].

The incidence is approximately 1 in 60 to 70 persons over the course of a lifetime, or 23 per 100,000 people annually[3]. It has a peak incidence between the ages of 10 and 40 and affects men and women about equally. Both the right and left sides of the face experience it equally frequently[4].

The underlying causes have been suggested to be genetics, autoimmune inflammatory diseases, vascular ischemia, and viral infection. Since the herpes simplex virus-1 genome was isolated from facial nerve endoneurial fluid in Bell's palsy patients, the idea that the condition is caused by a virus has gained traction[5].

The anatomical structure of the human face nerve, in particular its mixed neural profile comprising motor, sensory, and parasympathetic fibers, can be used to explain this clinical appearance of a rapid onset, unilateral, lower motor neuron-type facial weakness with accompanying symptoms of postauricular pain, dysgeusia subjective change in facial sensation and hyperacusis.. The sporadic occurrence of altered facial sensibility (cranial nerve V), vestibular dysfunction (cranial nerve VIII), or pharyngeal symptoms (cranial nerves IX and X) may possibly be explained by the facial nerve's tendency to create multiple connections with neighbouring cranial nerves[6,7]. The disorder causes the affected side of the face's facial muscles to become partially or completely incapable of being moved freely. Despite usually being self-limited, Bell's palsy-related facial paresis/paralysis can result in severe transient oral incompetence and an inability to seal the eyelid, which could cause ocular damage. There are other long-term negative consequences that might be extremely distressing for the patient[8].

Bell palsy is thought to result from compression of the seventh cranial nerve within the labyrinthine segment of the Fallopiian canal. Not only is this segment the narrowest along the nerve's course within the temporal bone, but it also appears to have the most tenuous blood supply, with very fine arterioles connecting the angiosomes supplied by the internal auditory branch of the anterior inferior cerebellar artery proximally and the petrosal branch of the middle meningeal artery distally [9]. Fortunately, over 95% of patients recover with timely pharmaceutical medication, and 70% to 80% of individuals will recover fully even without treatment. Rarely, surgery may be necessary to save the eye or enhance facial nerve function recovery[10].

This report presents a case of management of a case of Bells Palsy with antiviral and corticosteroid that were prescribed in the standard doses.

CASE REPORT

A 70 years old patient reported to the department of Oral and maxillofacial Surgery with chief complaint of pain and swelling in upper left back region of jaw from past 3 days. Pain was spontaneous on onset, continuous type and dull aching in nature. The patient gives history of severe headache, dizziness and fever since 1 week . Patient had habit of tobacco chewing since 40 years.

On extraoral examination it was noticed there was absence of wrinkles on left side of forehead, loss of nasolabial fold, drooping of left eye and corner of the mouth. Additionally, patient was also unable to close his left eye. The patient informed that these symptoms were lasting from 5 days but patient was unaware of his condition and so didn't show up to any doctor for the issue. A black coloured scar was seen extraorally in the same region extending from corner of the mouth to the canthus of the eye. The patient mentioned that it was due to insect bite(Figure 1).

Patient was informed about his condition and was questioned regarding any past history related to scar on the face. He denied any type of facial trauma or systemic alteration. Intraorally, Grade III mobility was present with 18.

From patients case history and examination, the diagnosis given was Unilateral Bell's palsy associated with Herpes Zoster infection although no HSV or herpes zoster lesions were present and Localised severe periodontitis with 18. The treatment plan was to prescribe antiviral and corticosteroids to the patient for management of Bell's Palsy and Extraction was to be carried out with 18.

The condition and treatment plan was thoroughly explained to the patient and an informed consent was obtained. Posterior superior alveolar nerve block was given to the patient using administration of local anaesthesia containing 2% lignocaine with 1:80,000 adrenaline and 18 was extracted atraumatically. Standard post operative management and instructions were given to the patient.

For Bell's Palsy, Patient was prescribed antiviral and corticosteroids for 5 days and was recalled after 5 days for followup (Table 1).

TABLE I: Medications Prescribed and their Dosage

Sr no	Medicine	Time	Dose	Days
1	Antiviral – Acyclovir	5 times	200 mg	5 days
2	Steroid -Dexamethasone	3 times	2 mg	5 days

Figure1: Pre treatment extraoral photograph

After 5 days patient was recalled and evaluated. Improvement was noticed in the condition of the patient. Tapering dose of medicine was continued for next 14 days and on followup complete recovery from the symptoms of Bell's Palsy was appreciated (Figure 2).

Figure2: Post treatment extraoral photograph

DISCUSSION

In this case report, we presented a case report of Unilateral Bell's Palsy associated with Herpes Zoster (Varicella Zoster Infection). Bell's palsy can be diagnosed with a variety of diseases, such as unilateral central facial weakness, Lyme neuroborreliosis, Ramsay Hunt syndrome, tumors, diabetes mellitus, sarcoidosis, weight loss, vertigo, visual abnormalities, and weakness or numbness[11].

Clinical signs, symptoms, and investigation to rule out other potential causes of facial paralysis are necessary for the diagnosis of Bell's palsy. The lumbar puncture, IgG and IgM antibody tests, and cerebral spinal fluid cell count are used to identify the cause of the paralysis. Magnetic resonance imaging and computed tomography are used to identify intracranial lesions or hemorrhages; the Lyme titre test is used to rule out Lyme disease; and the acetylcholine-receptor antibody test is used to identify myasthenia gravis[12].

IgG and IgM antibody titres were not available for our patients due to cost and resource constraints. Since no particular laboratory test can confirm the diagnosis of Bell's palsy, its assessment is still clinical, so even with IgG and IgM antibody tests, our clinical approach would have been the same. It is important to note that we followed these patients weekly and observed that they were recovering very well.

Additional research is necessary for patients who experience a second episode of palsy, involvement of other cranial nerves, or persistent clinical symptoms without recovery in facial paresis after four weeks. Those individuals should get a comprehensive clinical examination and a full history. To prevent misdiagnosis, it's critical to identify symptoms and indicators that are inconsistent with Bell's palsy as soon as possible. Imaging tests like computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging must be carried out if the patient does not recover in the anticipated amount of time. Occult lesions of the temporal bone, internal acoustic canal, or cerebellopontine angle, for instance, may be discovered using current imaging techniques[13].

In a retrospective study by Hwa Rim et al, suggested that f treatment approach and timing in Bell's palsy management should be informed by individual patient characteristics, including the severity of the condition. Favorable recovery outcomes were associated with treatment initiation within 72 h and steroid monotherapy. However, combinations of steroids and antiviral agents may have potential benefits, especially in patients with severe Bell's palsy[14].

In 2013, Lee et al conducted a clinical prospective study in which 206 patients were assigned randomly to treatment with a steroid or a combination of a steroid and an antiviral agent. The combination group showed a 2.6-times higher possibility of complete recovery than the steroid group. From the results of the study, the author concluded that clinicians should consider combination therapy with inert steroid and antiviral of choice in individuals with high-grade Bell's palsy within 1 week of onset and added that steroid plus antiviral treatment is more effective in treating severe to complete Bell's palsy than steroid treatment alone[15]. In a systematic review and meta analysis by Almeida et al, it was concluded that In Bell palsy, corticosteroids are associated with a reduced risk of unsatisfactory recovery. Antiviral agents, when administered with corticosteroids, may be associated with additional benefit[16].

Prednisone (60–80 mg/day) should be administered to a patient who has facial paralysis within a week, is not pregnant or diabetic, and shows no symptoms of infection. 10 days, followed by a gradual decline), in addition to 400 mg of acyclovir five times a day for 10 days. With just twice-daily dosage, oral valacyclovir, which the body converts to acyclovir, has a higher bioavailability than oral acyclovir and produces comparable acyclovir plasma concentrations[17]. Bell palsy patients may benefit from facial exercises. They consist of the following and ought to be carried out in front of a mirror: Blowing, whistling, opening and closing the eyes, and attempting to lift the eyebrows. You can do these exercises several times a day[18].

The treatment of our patient and the improvement that followed are consistent with previous research, which emphasizes the effectiveness of corticosteroid and antiviral therapy when taken together. The patient experienced little repercussions during follow-up, emphasising the significance of prompt management.

CONCLUSION

This case report presents a case showing lesion at stylomastoid foramen as only the signs of palsy affecting functions below the foramen are seen i.e. only the muscles of facial expression were affected. There was no loss of taste, no lack of salivation, lacrimation or loss of stapedial reflex (Hyperacusis) seen. Treatment with a steroid plus antiviral agent resulted in complete recovery. This combination therapy proved to be highly effective for management of Bell's Palsy.

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